

Soft Skills and Creativity Assessment in Students' Podcasts within the Framework of Teaching Excellence

Dorsaf Chaabane
Teacher
University of Carthage

Abstract

Today, in a world flipped by technology, soft skills including communication, problem solving and leadership, are becoming the hard skills of the 21st Century. In fact, education is converted into a purely digital act. Whether this unveils a utopia or a dystopia, critical thinking, emotional, social, cultural and digital intelligences shift into key assets in today's marketplace. The recent challenges triggered by technological advancement, a catalyst for the newly imposed status-quo, urge educators to rethink sustainable ways of teaching. The main challenge is exploring whether traditional teaching methods and assessment means could ride the waves of the digital metamorphosis in education and at the same time incorporate soft skills, which are inherently elusive, fluid and invisible, as a pivotal pillar to bolster curriculum design. The objective of this paper is to explore the efficacy of teaching excellence frameworks in creating sustainable ways of teaching soft skills in a digital era. To address the role of digital leadership in fostering teaching excellence and improving students experience and outcomes, a mixed methods approach was adopted, after taking the informed consent of higher education students at the undergraduate level. Data was collected through class activity, namely podcasts. An assessment of soft skills and creativity in the podcasts was conducted. The study reveals a significant correlation between soft skills development and creativity enhancement, a finding that advocates sustainable teaching excellence within the 21st century. In conclusion, this study provides insights into the application of innovative tools to cultivate soft skills in a student centered approach in an era marked by a ubiquitous digital transformation.

Keywords: soft skills, creativity, digital transformational leadership, sustainable teaching excellence.

Introduction

The terms "quality education" and "teaching excellence" in higher education remain ill-defined, as researchers continue to contemplate and debate over their various interpretations. (Brusoni et al., 2014; Greatbatch & Holland, 2016; Gunn & Fisk, 2013; Skelton, 2005, 2007). A universal understanding is rather challenging taking into consideration the different layers of influence including educational stakeholders and the particular and global contexts. According to a research by Cecilia Chan and Siaw Chen (2023), "teaching excellence is defined by the five dimensions of impact, innovation, inclusivity, scholarship of teaching and learning, and student-centredness, across six aspects of teaching including pedagogy, curriculum planning and design, assessment, student support, service to communities and professional development" Chan & Chen (2023).

To begin to explore "teaching excellence", it is first useful to consider the concept of quality in higher education. "Sustainable development goals of the United Nations for 2030" refer to "quality education" as a

cornerstone to a responsible teaching “SDG 4 (quality education)”. The premises of “quality education” entail that education should be universal, equal, inclusive and lifelong. In fact, “purposeful learning” is one of the pillars of “quality education” and it refers to making meaningful connections between what is learned and how it is applied in real world. “Purposeful learning” helps students to see the relevance and importance of what they are learning by setting clear learning outcomes, goals, autonomy and decisions. Furthermore, “quality education” is grounded in the respect of student's well-being. In fact, physical and emotional security matter most to students in order to feel safe, respected and valued “Maslow’s hierarchy of needs”. In a similar vein, it is well known that stress, anxiety, self-consciousness and lack of self-confidence and motivation make barriers to language learning “affective filters”.

“Balance and harmony” foster positive emotions which usher new synaptic portals to creativity Fredrickson (2004). ‘Creativity, openness, and curiosity’, also open new perspectives of divergent thinking, and the possibility of seeing beyond the silos of internal and external myopia. ‘Rhythm, balance and harmony’ become the gateway of possibility to innovation. Fredrickson (2004).

Another pillar of “quality education” is quality assessment which is grounded on setting clear tools to track development in language and skills, hence assessment of resources including quality content, books, programs, curriculum, materials, methods, ensures a high-quality learning experience. Heyworth, F.(2013). As Biggs, John. (2003) coined it: “ assessment will encourage better quality learning from the students, will equally certainly be more interesting for both the teacher and the students and will provide much more effective formative feedback to students.” Practically, there is a variety of alternative assessment methods or as As Biggs, John (2003) classified them ‘performance assessments’ including ‘practicum, seminar presentation, posters, interviewing, critical incidents, projects, reflective journals, case studies and problem solving, and portfolios’. Biggs, John (2003). We would like to add here the podcasting experience.

Creativity as a cornerstone for teaching excellence.

Innovation comes around as a pillar to teaching excellence. A major foundation for innovation is creativity. As Min Tang (2017) labelled it: “At a global level, our modern society is evolving from the “Information Age” to the “Creativity Age”. A unique feature of the creativity era is that ‘economies and societies’ are moving from “knowledge” to “creativity” as their key asset (Dubina, Carayannis, & Campbell, 2012) and that ‘economic activity’ is turning to ‘producing ideas’ rather than ‘producing things’ (Sawyer, 2012). In fact, the United Nations (UN) has listed “creativity” as ‘a core competence that students should develop in the UN Competency Development Guide’(United Nations, 2010) Min Tang (2017)

Min Tang (2017) adds: “In spite of the increasing awareness of the importance of creativity and innovation, scientific research into creativity and innovation is still non-mainstream due to the relatively short history of this field. In most cases, lay-persons and scholars alike tend to use the words “creativity”, “innovation”, “creative” or “innovative” interchangeably” Min Tang (2017). Indeed, from an academic perspective, there is a need to understand both creativity and innovation, and to found sound scientific methods to measure them, Min Tang (2017)

In fact, as Kaufman, J. C (2009) confirms that, today, “creativity is seen as a desired quality for admissions to graduate schools (Enright & Gitomer, 1989) and National Science Foundation grant applications (Lane, 1997). Moreover, creativity has been described as the most important economic resource of the 21st century (Florida, 2002)”. Kaufman, J. C (2009)

There is a solid research on the exact nature of creativity. However, debate is still ongoing over whether creativity is a construct related to personality and motivation, or to a special type of intelligence, in the framework of “Gardner’s multiple intelligences”. In fact, as Jung-Ho Jung reviewed it: “Overall, spatial and linguistic intelligences were positively related to creativity, while bodily kinesthetic and interpersonal intelligences were negatively related to creativity. » Jung-Ho Jung (2017)

The individual definition that Sawyer (2012, p. 7) proposed is “Creativity is a new mental combination that is expressed in the world”. According to Min Tang 2017, “three distinct features characterize this definition: (1) Creativity must be something new, novel, or original; (2) Creativity involves a combination of two or more

thoughts or concepts that have never been combined before by the individual; (3) Creativity must be expressed in a certain way in the world” Min Tang (2017).

In the same light, taking into consideration the importance of divergent thinking in creativity, Runco (2014) concluded that both hemispheres are involved in creativity: “It appears that both hemispheres are involved in divergent thinking (DT), and DT is accompanied by both event-related increases and decreases in the neural activation. There is a hint that the right hemisphere contributes more to DT. This is implied by the relatively high neural activation in the right central, temporal, and parietal regions during DT which is an indication of semantic processing and re-combination of semantically related information.” Runco (2014)

In this paper, we will look critically at some of the questions raised above when applying quality procedures in language education:

- What frameworks can be applied to soft skills’ teaching and assessment, namely creativity?
- To what extent do students’ podcasts exhibit creativite expression?

Literature review

Debunking skepticism about soft skills

Soft Skills are not Capstone Skills!

Soft skills are becoming the hard skills of the 21st Century. In today’s global job market, which is highly competitive, technical skills are no longer enough to stand out. They are insufficient for workers to rank high. “Soft skills are of paramount importance” says Susan A. Dean (2019). In the same vein, in her article “Which are harder, soft skills or hard skills?” Pieterse V. (2016) reports that “Building successful software development projects does not only entail technical aspects but also the people that are involved in developing the particular software. The performance of people is affected by external factors such as stress, and internal factors such as cognitive ability, but the literature about the connection between personality and performance is overlooked.” Hence, the success of hard skills is related to soft skills, this is supported by researchers in the field of engeneering Pieterse V (2016), let alone other fields such as medicine and aviation (Bhatt V.2023), architecture (Ruth, Stevens. 2023) and finance (Slezák, Jiří 2024). In fact, Farmer, D.L. (2015) studied the importance of soft skills in surgery: “In today’s world of team training, team science, and interprofessional education, the importance of these soft skills cannot be understated” Farmer, D.l.(2015)

Lamri (2023) argued that “Although hard and soft skills have different definitions and uses, they also overlap to some degree (Green 2011; Cinque 2016). For example, communication, although traditionally categorised as a soft skill, also involves technical aspects like data analysis and writing, using software to produce presentations. Similarly, interpersonal skills include specific knowledge about group behaviour and social codes, which could be seen as a hard skill (Bishop 2017)” Lamri (2023). Also, Lamri questions: “Is the distinction between hard/soft useful? Is there, metaphorically, a scale of “hardness” of skills, like Mohs’ scale for the hardness of minerals, ranging from talc (very soft) to diamonds (very hard)?” Lamri (2023)

“Soft skills” is a Pseudo-Science

Misinformation can be harmful. We need to highlight the differences between scientific inquiry and pseudoscience. Scientific enquiry is submitted to a rigorous process of testing and verification, however pseudoscience often lacks these elements. Soft skills are mostly considered as an intruder to the field of psychology especially with the fact that practitioners in the world of coaching are not exposed to strict and rigid assessment and that the new business of coaching is in full expansion. However, soft skills as an academic and scientific subject should be rooted in scientific studies in different fields, notably, psychology, philosophy, medicine, social sciences, management and related fields.

“Soft Skills” is a Marketing Word, a Buzzword

Mathiew Charles (2018), in his article “Teaching In Spite Of Excellence” states that “Readings’ characterized “excellence” is symptomatic of the “Americanization” of higher education.” Bill Readings

(1996), in his book *'The University In Ruins'* confirms the idea that the university is not immune to the effects of consumerism.

Cörvers, F. (2009) adds that “research and higher education transformed gradually to the American standard. Costs as well as benefits of the Americanization of European higher education and research seem to be to a large extent related to the acceptance of English as the lingua franca and to the specific content of what is taught and investigated” Frank Cörvers (2009)

Selling the illusion of becoming, but becoming what? We are at the age of marketing by excellence. The marketing industry is ubiquitous. Today, not only goods are marketed but also values, especially in the field of education and recruitment. Crawford F. (2001) highlights that “the simple fact is that people are so hungry for basic human values, values they are not experiencing in their day-to-day lives, that they will flock to a company that provides them” Crawford F. (2001). For example, it is estimated that Extraversion is a highly solicited personality trait in professions, but should all people become extraverted, should all become leaders taking into consideration team dynamics and group roles?

The word soft skills, sometimes is labeled as “transversal competencies”, “generic competencies”, “21st century skills”, “Four C’s”, “Emotional intelligence”, “Transferable skills”, “Life skills”, “Power skills”, and “Employability skills”. These names are often used more as “advertising or promotional labels for overlapping skills” Lucas (2019) using buying words, that sell, that catch the attention of educational consumers.

Soft Skills cannot be Taught

Whether a person can change his level of intelligence or personality type or “emotional intelligence” is still a subject of debate. For instance, Haier RJ (2014) refutes the idea that levels of intelligence can be improved with training; “So far, we do not have it for claims about increasing intelligence after cognitive training or, for that matter, any other manipulation or treatment, including early childhood education. Small statistically significant changes in test scores may be important observations about attention or memory or some other elemental cognitive variable or a specific mental ability assessed with a ratio scale like milliseconds, but they are not sufficient proof that general intelligence has changed.” Haier RJ (2014)

However, Jackson, J.J (2024) is more optimistic about personality changes, to some extent: “Although personality is relatively stable across the lifespan, there is also ample evidence that it is malleable.”, “When change does occur, it is often modest in scale. Ultimately, it is difficult to cultivate a completely different personality, but small changes are possible.” Jackson, J.J(2024)

Another controversial evidence about “emotional intelligence” (EI) improvement with training is presented by a meta-analysis made by Hodzic, S, et al (2017): “From a theoretical standpoint, much has been discussed about plasticity of EI and whether it can be learned and developed. The obtained results show that specific interventions improve EI”. However, “these trainings

focused on increasing the explicit knowledge, enhancing the awareness about different emotional abilities or aspects of EI, not on how they actually respond in every-day situations” Hodzic, S, et al (2017). This means that improvements touch on the first level of emotional intelligence, which is self-awareness, but not on the second level, which is self regulation. As Hodzic, S, et al (2017) adds, this needs cascading knowledge: “Hence, in order to translate this knowledge into practice (to enhance the procedural knowledge) and in order for it to have observable benefits, repetitive and longer trainings are needed.” Hodzic, S, et al (2017)

Why Soft Skills Matter

‘Soft skills’ include a broad range of competences such as intrapersonal and interpersonal skills, Emotional, social and cultural intelligence, communication and leadership, team dynamics, negotiation, digital, media and employability skills, study skills, problem solving and creativity, to frame it simply. Deepa, S (2013) states that: “In recent years, the corporate world felt that soft skills are crucial at the workplace and its training must be a part of the curriculum during education. In career terms, soft skills soften the edges and provide a competitive advantage over others. However, those who ignore this critical aspect of personality learn its importance the hard way when their promotion is overlooked” Deepa, S (2013)

A comprehensive framework for soft skills is the ‘P21 Core Literacy Framework’ as presented in fig.1:

FIGURE 1
p21 Core literacy framework.

Source: <https://www.battelleforkids.org/networks/p21>

Soft Skills and Recruitment

Studies have recently focused on the impact interpersonal skills and personality characteristics have on employability (Heckman and Kautz, 2012; Succi, 2019; Wheeler, 2016.)

Different tests are commonly used for recruitment. For instance, Stewart, Susan (2023) summarized testing tools for hiring business leaders. These tests include personality traits according to “the big five personality test”, “Leadership style” assessment, critical thinking tests as well as “Emotional intelligence” tests.

Another trend in recruitment is using digital media. The status quo for recruitment involves using social media platforms in addition to video self-recording, that is using self-presentations instead of paper based CVs, real-time video interviews and other techniques, and here we notice the importance of digital and media skills in employment. Solanki,(2024)

Personality Tests

A variety of tests have been used to unearth the personality type of job candidates. According to Reman P. (2021) The “Big five personality trait test” is widely used to study “openness, agreeableness, extraversion, conscientiousness and neuroticism”.

Another test is the ‘DISC’, which is an acronym for ‘dominance, Influence, steadiness, and Conscientiousness’. These traits are usually tested to be either active or reactive.

The “Myers-Briggs Type Indicator” (MBTI), which is based on the Carl Jung theory, is based on the interaction of energy, action, and reflection. As reported by King & Manson, (n.d), “the extrovert gains power through action and loses it through reflection, whereas, the introverted loses energy from the action and gains energy from reflection” (King & Manson, n.d.).

As Reman P. (2021) reports, “many organizations widely use these tests for recruitment despite the doubts about their accuracy, reliability and validity” (En, Lan, Tay & Ng, 2011). Reman P. (2021)

Intelligence Tests and Recruitment

“Gardners intelligence types” tests are an invaluable tool for recruitment to pinpoint strengths and weaknesses in candidates. It is important to match the type of intelligence(s) to fit the task requirements. Some jobs require distinguished linguistic intelligence, while others call for “logical-mathematical”, “interpersonal intelligence”, “intrapersonal”, “spatial”, “bodily-kinesthetic”, or “musical intelligence”. Likewise, some jobs require a unique mix of intelligence types. Thus knowing oneself, preferences and strengths can enhance “self-efficacy”, loyalty motivation and excellence.

Measuring Creativity: Frameworks

According to Rababah, L.(2018): "The importance of creativity assessment has been noted as early as the 1960s in the area of creativity research (Guilford, 1967; Sternberg, 2006; Torrance, 1965). Treffinger (1987) claimed that the justification behind the assessment of creativity was to establish baseline data that are useful in diagnosing students' needs and curricula" Rababah, L.(2018). Moreover, "Starko (2013) also addressed the need for creativity enhancement, stating that the efforts expended to improve creativity in students appeared to be doomed to failure unless the root of creativity is determined (Starko, 2013; Wang, Fussell, & Cosley, 2011)." Rababah, L.(2018). Rababah, L.(2018) affirms that creativity assessment becomes a fundamental step towards excellence.

The "Torrance Test" of Creative Thinking (TTCT)

The "Torrance Test of Creative Thinking" (TTCT) was created by Guilford (1967) and Torrance (1965) in the aim of creativity assessment. As claimed by Rababah, L.(2018): "An Adapted version of TTCT encompasses three EFL/ESL creative writing aspects, namely, fluency, flexibility and originality" Rababah, L.(2018).

Rababah et al. (2013) described fluency as "the ability of the individual to produce novel ideas", flexibility as "the ability of the individual to produce various ideas" and originality as "the ability of the individual to produce distinct and personal ideas and solutions to problems." Again, fluency refers to the number of ideas, flexibility is about providing various categories in answers, and originality entails considering innovative answers that are neither familiar nor unsuitable. Rababah, L.(2018)

The "Consensual Assessment" (CAT)

Csikszentmihalyi (1994, p. 8) developed the "Consensual Assessment Technique" (CAT), which gathers experts in a specific domain to evaluate creative outcomes. CAT is widely used for creativity assessment. Phonethibsavads (2019) suggests that: "CAT has become a standard because it utilizes a panel of experts to appraise the creativity of final products." Thus, for example, a CAT qualitative study of major elements in drama (creativity assessment by experts in students' drama performances) concluded that elements like uniqueness, engagement, energy, authenticity, boldness and freedom of expression were insightful for evaluating creative expression. Phonethibsavads (2019)

The "Four C's Model" of Creativity

The "Four C's model of creativity" was developed by James Kaufman and Ronald Beghetto. It describes four levels of creativity that align through a spectrum. The model starts from internal transformation to external impact reminding us of the circles of concern, influence and control introduced by Stephen Covey in his book "the seven habits of highly effective people", "The four Cs model" underscores the power of creativity though. "The four C's model" is a proof that creativity is a culprit for change and transformation. This is advocated by Albrechts, L (2005) in his article 'Creativity as a Drive for Change', he stated that "Because society is not a prisoner of its past and because it has a responsibility for the future, it is doomed to find alternatives. It is doomed to study the forces of change and to look for means and instruments to make this change happen. This means that we need to structurally transform our attitudes to the natural environment and our relationships with others (especially 'the other'). Such transformation requires structural reforms in power relationships to tackle the overpowering" Albrechts, L (2005)

In a nutshell, Kaufman, J.C., & Beghetto, R.A. (2009) confirm that "We believe that at the Pro-c (and Big-C) level, extrinsic and intrinsic motivation both help shape and prod creative activity."

Source: Kaufman, J. C., & Beghetto, R. A. (2009).

Research Methodology

A mixed research approach including quantitative and qualitative studies was conducted. Correlational rates were reviewed to confirm the hypothesis that soft skills are interrelated to creativity. 100 podcasts from a total of 400 podcasts made over 2 years by undergraduate English language students were studied. 50 podcasts made in semester one were compared to 50 podcasts in semester two, in order to see if there were any improvements.

Data Analysis

A random sampling of primary sources of data, which are podcasts created by students at the undergraduate level of English language studies, was analysed. The podcasts included voice only. Special digital effects were added by students. Body language was not under study at this level because the focus was not on video recordings.

Methodology

Soft skills were tested through assessment of skills including empathy, storytelling, critical thinking, originality of topics, divergent thinking, digital tools, presence, and voice management. Creative thinking was tested using a variety of tools. First, “The Torrance Test” of Creative Thinking (TTCT) Including the following elements fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration. Second, “The Four C Model” of Kaufman, J. C., & Beghetto, R. A. was used to test levels of creative expression in students works. A correlational approach was applied to see whether high levels of soft skills match high levels of creativity using these different tests.

Results

Discussion

A significant level of soft skills is expressed in the podcasts. Empathy, voice management and storytelling are highly marked. However, critical and divergent thinking needed more diligence. Lower rates go to digital skills, a thing that could be explained by the fast development of the digital world.

Empathy was measured mainly through voice, whether cold or emotional, word choice, and the intended selection of a sensitive topic or a current issue including environment, peace, illegal immigration, personal and social values, culture, relationships, mindset, emotional, social and cultural intelligence, or other. Critical and analytical thinking was elicited mainly through the depth of reflection and skills including defying and exposing mainstream mentality, unveiling logical fallacies and cognitive biases in thinking, challenging misconceptions and stereotypes. In fact, a considerable number of podcasts exposed dilemmas or unspoken topics such as bullying, sexism, prejudice, and other highly critical topics. Divergent thinking was assessed through the unique choice of topics and themes, and the way ideas were presented. All of that was possible through measuring novelty, new associations like the combination of sounds and music background with pictures or videos, the use of digital tools, coding or the use of applications or subtitles, presenting data in an innovative manner and not to forget, using sarcasm, humor, voice over, memes or even drawings. Overall, there are some novel ideas that are not copied or have a sense of déjà-vu as a result of repetition of the same topics presentation.

A striking finding was the correlation between high levels of empathy, storytelling, voice manipulation and creativity, notably in “The Torrance test”. This finding was advocated by scholars, namely Anderson, S (2023) and Carlozzi, A. F.(1995). The finding supports the hypothesis that empathy is linked to creativity and that “linguistic intelligence” or expressiveness is another factor leading to, or is associated with creativity.

This finding supports the idea that creativity is not the sole product of logical mathematical intelligence; however, the role of other types of intelligence in creativity should not be neglected. As Runco, (2014) concluded “ It appears that both hemispheres are involved in divergent thinking (DT)” Runco, (2014). Thus, what leads to creativity is the synaptic or neural activation in either hemisphere.

Limitations and Recommendations

Despite the scope of research on creativity assessment, certain limitations emerge, particularly the overlapping incidence or recurrence between soft skills and the “Torrance Test” elements, such as speaking abilities and divergent thinking. In this study, students were not explicitly required to prioritize creativity in the podcasts, yet they valued it implicitly, especially since the podcasting task contributed to their grade. Although it accounted only for 10% of the final mark, students demonstrated a strong intrinsic motivation to complete the task with precision. This suggests that alternative formative assessment tools can serve as powerful motivational channels for students to express their creativity and personal voice. Furthermore, integrating a "teacher-as-a-coach" approach should be advocated even in hard skills subjects, as it fosters autonomy, engagement, and curiosity.

Conclusion

This research underscores the growing significance of soft skills and creativity in today’s dynamic and rapidly evolving digital landscape. The findings suggest that while technical expertise remains important, it is the combination of soft skills and innovative thinking that drives long-term success and adaptability. Creativity is fostered by quality teaching. Teaching excellence can be achieved through alternative assessment means, formative assessment and explicit teaching of soft skills. Not to mention the importance of their integration in hard skills subjects, as they become an undeniable drive for employability. Our findings highlight that creativity should be seen through a broader lens, not only as a “logical-mathematical” artefact but also as an asset of all thinking styles. Its power should not be under-estimated as it is an instrument of “transformational leadership” to drive change. In fact, the future is creativity.

References

1. Albrechts, Louis. (2005). Creativity as a Drive for Change Planning Theory p.247-269. doi 10.1177/1473095205058496. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/249742412>
2. Anderson, S., Cameron, C. D., & Beaty, R. E. (2023). Creative Empathy. *Creativity Research Journal*, 37(1), 71–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2023.2229649>
3. Anthony Phonethibsavads, Kylie Pepler, Sophia Bender.(2019). Utilizing the Consensual Assessment Technique to Compare Creativity in Drama Spaces. *Creativity. Theories – Research – Applications* vol 6(1)
4. <https://www.battelleforkids.org/networks/p21>
5. Bhatt V. (2023). Soft skills for personal development of the surgeon for improved outcomes for patient and surgeon. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg*. May-Aug;14(2):161-166. doi: 10.4103/njms.njms_103_23. Epub 2023 Jul 13. PMID: 37661978; PMCID: PMC10474545.
6. Biggs, John. (2003). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*.
 1. Carlozzi, A. F., Bull, K. S., Eells, G. T., & Hurlburt, J. D. (1995). Empathy as Related to Creativity, Dogmatism, and Expressiveness. *The Journal of Psychology*, 129(4), 365–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1995.9914974>
 2. Charles, M. (2018).Teaching, in Spite of Excellence: Recovering a Practice of Teaching-Led Research. *Stud Philos Educ* 37, (15–29). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11217-017-9568-1>
 3. Crawford F.& Mathiew R. (2001).The myth of excellence.Why great companies never try to be the best at everything. *Cap Gemini Ernst & Young. Random house.inc*. ISBN: 0609 608-29
 4. Cörvers, Frank & Borghans, Lex (2009). The Americanization of European Higher Education and Research. -Doi - 10.2139/ssrn.148926- SSRN Electronic Journal

5. ER - Deepa, S; Seth, Manisha. (2013): Do Soft Skills Matter? - Implications for Educators Based on Recruiters' Perspective- *IUP Journal of Soft Skills*; vol1 , 7-20.
6. Farmer DL. (2015) Soft Skills Matter. *JAMA Surg.* ;150(3):207. doi:10.1001/jamasurg.2014.2250
7. Frank Heyworth (2013). Applications of quality management in language education. *Language Teaching*, 46, pp 281315 doi:10.1017/S0261444813000025
8. Fredrickson BL. (2004) The broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 2004 Sep 29;359(1449):1367-78. doi: 10.1098/rstb..1512. PMID: 15347528; PMCID: PMC1693418.
9. Haier RJ. (2014) Increased intelligence is a myth (so far). *Front Syst Neurosci.* Mar 12;8:34. doi: 10.3389/fnsys.2014.00034. PMID: 24659957; PMCID: PMC3950413.
10. Hodzic, Sabina ,et al. (2017). How Efficient Are Emotional Intelligence Trainings: A Meta-Analysis. *Emotion Review.* 10. 10.1177/1754073917708613.
11. Jung-Ho Jung & Don-Ryun Chang. (2016). Types of creativity—Fostering multiple intelligences in design convergence talents. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, Vol 23, P 101-111, ISSN 1871-1871, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc>.
12. Jackson, J. J., & Wright, A. J. (2024). The process and mechanisms of personality change. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 3(5), 305–318. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-024-00295-z>
13. Ka Yuk Chan, C., & Chen, S. W. (2023). Conceptualisation of teaching excellence: an analysis of teaching excellence schemes. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 49(4), 485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2023.2271188>
14. Kaufman, J. C., & Beghetto, R. A. (2009). Beyond Big and Little: The Four C Model of Creativity. *Review of General Psychology*, 13(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0013688> (Original work published 2009)
15. Lamri, Jeremy & Lubart, Todd. (2023). Reconciling Hard Skills and Soft Skills in a Common Framework: The Generic Skills Component Approach. *Journal of Intelligence.* 11. 107. 10.3390/jintelligence11060107.
16. Matthew Charles. (2017). Teaching, in Spite of Excellence: Recovering a Practice of Teaching-Led Research. *Springerlink.com*
17. Min Tang. (2017). Creativity and Innovation: Basic Concepts and Approaches. Chapter 1. b2590 *Handbook of the Management of Creativity and Innovation: Theory and Practice..*
18. Muhammad Nadeem Anwar, et al. (2012). A Comparison of Creative Thinking Abilities of High and Low Achievers Secondary School Students. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education -*, Volume 1, Issue 1
19. <https://www.normanjackson.co.uk/creative-academic/the-four-c-model-of-creativity>
20. Pieterse, Vreda & Eekelen, Marko. (2016). Which Are Harder? Soft Skills or Hard Skills?- Conference: Annual Conference of the Southern African Computer Lecturers' Association.. *Communications in Computer and Information Science* 642:160-167 doi - 10.1007/978-3-319-47680-3_15
21. Rababah, Luqman. (2018). An adapted version of Torrance Test of creative thinking (ttct) in efl/esl writing: a rubric scoring and a review of studies - *International Journal of English and Education*, vol - 7
22. Readings, Bill. (1996). *The university in Ruins*. Cambridge, MA/London: Harvard University Press.
23. Reman, Patrik & Nordin, Angelika. (2021). Personality tests in recruitment. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349466573>
24. Runco, M.A., Yoruk, S. (2014). The Neuroscience of Divergent Thinking. *Act Nerv Super* 56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03379602>
25. Ruth, Stevens. (2023). Investing in soft skills in (interior) architectural design education?!. 10.21606/drsldx.2024.087.
26. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
27. Slezák, Jiří. (2024). The importance of soft skills in accounting: student's and employer's expectations. *Acta Universitatis Bohemiae Meridionalis.* 27. 42-57. 10.32725/acta.2024.004.
28. Solanki & Gujarati. (2024) The Digital Revolution In Recruitment: Unraveling The Impact And Challenges Of E-Recruitment -*Educational Administration Theory and Practices VL* - 30. doi - 10.53555/kuey.v30i6(s).5362

29. Stewart, Susan. (2023) The role of tests and assessments for hiring and developing business leaders. *Journal of Strategic and International Studies* Volume XVII Number 1 ISSN 2326-3636
30. The Americanization of European Higher Education. · (2009) SSRN Electronic Journal doi: 10.2139/ssrn.1489268 ·
31. Vreda Pieterse, et al (2016). Which Are Harder? Soft Skills or Hard Skills? - Conference: Annual Conference of the Southern African Computer Lecturers' Association. *Communications in Computer and Information Science* 642:160-167. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-47680-3_15

